

Solvent effects and ion-solvent interactions from the studies of the solubility and dissociation constants of oxalic acid in aquo + 2-propanol mixtures and determination of single-ion Gibbs energies of transfer from water to 2-propanol + H₂O mixtures

S. K. Gumtya^a and S. C. Lahiri^{a,b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kalyani University, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal, India

^bResearch Advisor, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, 30D, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : sujitclahiri@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The solvent effects on the dissociation of the simplest dibasic organic acid were examined from the determination of the first and second dissociation constants of oxalic acid conductometrically and pH-metrically in water + 2-propanol mixtures (0–87 wt% of 2-propanol). The solubility values of oxalic acid and potassium hydrogen oxalate were also determined. The dissociation constants and the solubility values were used to calculate the Gibbs energies of transfer ΔG_t^0 of oxalic acid (H₂OX), bioxalate (HOX⁻), oxalate (OX²⁻) and potassium (K⁺) ions from water to aquo-propanolic mixtures. These represent the 'medium effects' or quantitative measures of solute or ion-solvent interactions of the respective species in going from water to 2-propanol + water mixtures. pK_1 , pK_2 and the solubility values of oxalic acid increase continuously with increase in organic co-solvent. ΔG_t^0 (H₂OX) and ΔG_t^0 (H⁺) are negative i.e. favourable but ΔG_t^0 (H₂OX), ΔG_t^0 (OX²⁻) and ΔG_t^0 (K⁺) are in general positive and hence unfavourable for the dissociation processes. The increase in basicity facilitated the dissociation processes but decrease in dielectric constant and H-bonding capability enhances the association processes as the organic co-solvent increases.

The pK -values can be suitably utilised to prepare buffer solutions in 2-propanol + water mixtures. The solvent effect and solvation phenomena can be better understood from the collection of single-ion values of transfer. These may be utilised to calculate the solubilities of electrolytes in 2-propanol + water mixtures.

Attempts have been made to understand the solvation processes in terms of the structure of the aquo-organic mixtures and Walden products.

Keywords : Gibbs energies of transfer of single-ions, ion-solvent interactions, medium effect, oxalic acid, solubility, thermodynamic dissociation constants, 2-propanol + water mixtures, Walden product.

Introduction

One of the difficulties associated with measurements of the dissociation constants of acids in mixed or non-aqueous solvents is the accurate determination of H⁺ ion concentrations in mixed or non-aqueous solvents. The usual convention is to refer electrode potentials in each solvent to the arbitrary zero of standard hydrogen electrode in the same solvent which, however, generates quite a large number of thermodynamically unrelated pH or e.m.f. scales as there are solvents¹. The correlation of the pK -values in different solvents is thus difficult.

The nominal value of pH in different solvents does not necessarily imply equal proton activities in different

solvents, because \bar{G}_H^0 would vary with the varying acid-base properties of solvents². Thus, the accurate determination of H⁺ ion activity demands an exact knowledge of the 'medium effect' which is as yet proved to be elusive^{3,4}.

In search of a suitable method which could avoid uncertainties due to liquid-junction potential and changed sensitivity of the glass electrode⁵ (as in pH-metric or potentiometric method) we found that the conductometric method can be well adopted with success⁶.

The pK -values determined conductometrically can be utilised for the preparation of buffers in mixed solvents which can be utilised for the measurement of pH-value of

the mixed solvents.

Studies on the solvent effect on electrolytes are of great importance in understanding the properties of solutions and the ion-solvent interactions, the controlling force in dilute solutions where ion-ion interactions are assumed to be negligible⁷⁻¹¹. Analysis of the effects of solvents can give useful information on ion-solvent interactions and single ion (transfer) value of inorganic and organic ions¹²⁻²³.

The considerations led us to undertake a systematic study of the solubility, the first and second dissociation constants of oxalic acid in different mono-ol + water solvents. The present investigation of the solubility and dissociation constants of oxalic acid in 2-propanol + water mixtures is a continuation of our earlier works^{24,25}. The results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Oxalic acid $H_2C_2O_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ (G.R., E. Merck) was used as such. Estimation of oxalic acid, preparation of potassium hydrogen oxalate and other experimental details were described before^{24,25}.

2-Propanol (A.R., E. Merck) was treated with pre-heated CaO, kept over night and distilled. The middle fraction (b.p. 355.2 K, $n_D = 1.375$ at 298 K) was collected for use¹⁹. The physical properties of binary mixtures (2-PrOH + H_2O) are given in Table 1^{26,27}.

Table 1. Physical parameters of the solutions (2-propanol + H_2O mixtures) at 298 K

2-Propanol (wt%)	Mole fraction	$1/\epsilon \times 10^2$	η (C.P.)	A
0	0	1.27	0.8903	0.509
8.0	0.0254	1.37	1.28	0.566
16.3	0.0914	1.50	1.807	0.648
25.1	0.0924	1.65	2.337	0.747
34.3	0.1354	1.86	2.739	0.895
43.9	0.1901	2.13	2.961	1.096
54.0	0.2605	2.52	3.074	1.411
64.6	0.3538	3.10	2.997	1.925
75.8	0.4844	3.87	2.766	2.685
87.5	0.6774	4.72	2.399	3.618
100	1.0	5.56	2.035	4.636

ϵ = Relative permittivity or dielectric constant.

η = Viscosity.

$$A = \frac{1.822 \times 10^6}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}}, \quad A \text{ is a constant for the solvent at the specified temperature } T.$$

Solubility of oxalic acid and potassium hydrogen oxalate in water and 2-propanol + water mixtures were determined using a Campbell solubility²⁸ apparatus kept in a thermostat controlled at 298 ± 0.02 K.

For the determination of the first dissociation constants of oxalic acid in different solvents, conductances of solutions containing different concentrations (8×10^{-4} – 5×10^{-3} M) of oxalic acid and potassium hydrogen oxalate (1.6×10^{-3} – 1×10^{-2} M) were measured. The second dissociation constants of the acid were determined pH-metrically. The H^+ ion concentrations of neutralised solutions of potassium hydrogen oxalate of known concentrations were also determined.

Conductance measurements were done with a Kyoto (Japan) Electronics conductivity bridge (Model CM-115), with a special conductance cell supplied by the manufacturer. The cell constant (1.009 cm^{-1}) was checked repeatedly by measuring conductances of standard KCl solutions as recommended by Jones and Bradshaw²⁹. The measurements were done at 298 ± 0.02 K.

Calibration of the glass electrode :

The pH measurements were made using an Orion expandable pH-meter (Model EATM-940). The calibration of the glass electrode and measurements of H^+ ion concentrations in 2-PrOH + H_2O were made in the way described before^{24,25,30,31}.

The resolution of the pH-meter is 0.001 pH unit. However, in view of the change in asymmetric potential and liquid junction potential of uncertain magnitude in going from water to mixed solvents, the meter reading were rounded to 0.01 unit.

Results

The dissociation of oxalic acid can be presented as

and

The thermodynamic dissociation constants for reactions (1) and (2) can be written as

$$K_1 = \frac{C_{H^+} \times C_{HOX^-}}{C_{H_2OX}} \times \frac{\gamma_{H^+} \times \gamma_{HOX^-}}{\gamma_{H_2OX}} \quad (3)$$

and

$$K_2 = \frac{C_{H^+} \times C_{OX^{2-}}}{C_{HOX^-}} \times \frac{\gamma_{H^+} \times \gamma_{OX^{2-}}}{\gamma_{HOX^-}} = K'_2 \cdot \gamma_{OX^{2-}} (\gamma_{H^+} = \gamma_{HOX^-}) \quad (4)$$

γ represents the respective activity coefficients. In dilute solutions γ_{H_2OX} of the uncharged H_2OX can be assumed to be unity.

For the conductometric determination of the first dissociation constants, the equivalent conductances Λ of H_2OX at different concentrations were measured. The data (Λ against C) are presented in Table 2a.

The conductance data were analysed using Shedlovsky's method^{32,33}. The sets of equation used are given below :

$$\frac{1}{S\Lambda} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \frac{CS\Lambda\gamma_{\pm}^2}{K_1\Lambda_0^2} \quad (5)$$

(K_1 = dissociation constant)

$$\beta = \frac{8.204 \times 10^5 \Lambda_0}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} + \frac{82.5}{\eta(\epsilon T)^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

$$S = \left[\frac{\beta(\Delta C)^{1/2}}{2\Lambda_0^{3/2}} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\beta(\Delta C)^{1/2}}{2\Lambda_0^{3/2}} \right)^2} \right]^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{S\Lambda}{\Lambda_0} \quad (8)$$

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{1.8246 \times 10^6 (C\alpha)^{1/2}/(\epsilon T)^{3/2}}{1 + 50.29 \times 10^8 r (C\alpha)^{1/2}/(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \quad (9)$$

' r ' is taken to be equal to the Bjerrum critical distance ' q '³⁴ i.e.

$$q = r = \frac{e^2}{2\epsilon kT} \quad (10)$$

The terms have their usual significance. The viscosity coefficients and the relative permittivities (dielectric constants) of the aquo-organic mixtures were taken from the literature²⁶. The initial values of Λ_0 were obtained from the plot of $1/\Lambda$ against ΔC utilising the relation,

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \frac{1}{K\Lambda_0^2} (\Delta C) \quad (11)$$

The dissociation constant (K_1) and the limiting equivalent conductance Λ_0 -values were iteratively calculated by a least square treatment fitted to eqs. (5-10). The values of the slopes were accepted only when the values of the regression coefficients were 0.99 or better.

However, accurate Λ_0 -values of the oxalic acid were calculated from the relation

$$\Lambda_{0(H_2OX)} = \Lambda_{0(KHOX)} + \Lambda_{0(HClO_4)} - \Lambda_{0(KClO_4)} \quad (12)$$

and were utilised to calculate K_1 . The values of $\Lambda_{0(HClO_4)}$ and $\Lambda_{0(KClO_4)}$ were taken from works previously reported^{19,22}.

Λ_0 -values of KHOX (potassium hydrogen oxalate) were obtained from the plot of Λ against $-\sqrt{c}$ (Table 2b). However, in view of the possibility of ion-association for KHOX, accurate Λ_0 and association constant ($1/K_1$) values were obtained using the set of eqs. (5-10) in the way described before.

The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 2(a). Equivalent conductances Λ of oxalic acid in different concentrations of 2-propanol + H_2O mixtures at 298 K

Concentration $C \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	Λ (S cm ² equiv ⁻¹) in wt% of 2-propanol									
	0	8	16.3	25.1	34.3	43.9	54	64.6	75.8	87.5
0.8	-	310.7	238.4	183.5	133.6	101.6	69.9	41.0	36.4	18.6
1	383.5	308.6	236.7	181.8	131.9	99.1	67.7	39.4	34.4	17.0
2	375.3	300.3	229.9	174.4	126.5	91.5	61.1	32.7	28.3	13.2
3	366.2	293.5	222.2	168.6	120.6	86.0	56.0	29.6	25.1	11.5
4	362.1	284.6	215.9	162.2	115.7	81.8	52.3	26.9	22.7	10.2
5	359.7	279.7	210.7	158.6	110.6	77.4	49.4	24.9	20.7	9.3
6	353.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2(b). Equivalent conductances Λ of KH oxalate in different concentrations of 2-propanol + H₂O mixtures at 298 K

Concentration $C \times 10^3$ (g-equiv dm ⁻³)	Λ (S cm ² equiv ⁻¹) in wt% of 2-propanol									
	0	8	16.3	25.1	34.4	43.9	54	64.6	75.8	87.5
1.6	-	74.11	57.7	42.0	32.6	25.6	20.3	16.8	13.4	11.4
2	101.8	71.8	55.9	40.8	31.9	24.7	20.2	17.2	14.1	11.2
4	95.9	67.9	52.7	37.5	29.2	23.7	19.1	15.9	12.8	10.2
6	93.1	65.1	48.8	34.8	28.5	22.7	18.2	15.4	12.3	9.8
8	87.9	63.8	47.9	33.9	28.0	21.1	17.8	14.2	11.8	9.0
10	82.9	63.1	45.4	30.9	26.7	21.2	16.9	14.1	11.0	8.6
12	82.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3. Solubility, equivalent conductances and dissociation constants of KHOX and oxalic acid in 2-propanol + H₂O mixtures at 298 K

2-Propanol (wt%)	Mole fraction	Solubility (mol dm ⁻³)		Λ_0 (S cm ² equiv ⁻¹)								
		KHOX	Oxalic acid	HClO ₄	KClO ₄	KHOX		Oxalic acid			pK ₁	pK ₂
						A	B	A	B	C		
0	0	0.415	1.17	417.7	141.4	114	110.9	389	391.2	387.2	1.276	4.27
									(390) ^a		(1.27) ^a	(4.27) ^a
8.0	0.0254	0.260	1.094	348.4	109.2	81	76.4	318.5	321.2	315.6	1.54	4.83
16.3	0.0552	0.201	1.144	266.7	79.5	63	62.1	246.3	248.3	249.3	1.63	5.10
25.1	0.0914	0.144	1.175	220.6	62.4	48	47.0	192.3	192.1	205.2	1.73	5.37
34.3	0.1354	0.096	1.238	163.6	59.5	37	34.3	141.8	143.7	138.4	1.89	5.63
43.9	0.1901	0.061	1.30	138.6	48.9	28	27.1	111.1	112.6	114.8	2.17	5.98
54.0	0.2605	0.040	1.313	106.3	39.9	23	22.0	78.1	82.2	8.4	2.42	6.34
64.6	0.3538	0.020	1.325	74.7	34.6	20	18.8	54.0	57.7	58.9	2.89	6.76
75.8	0.4844	0.009	1.363	71.8	30.2	16	15.5	50.0	56.9	57.1	3.10	7.26
87.5	0.6774	0.0036	1.412	56.7	27.0	13	13.4	31.3	38.5	43.1	3.55	7.60
100	1.0	0.0018	1.764									

A = From graph of Λ vs \sqrt{C} for KHOX and from graph of $1/\Lambda$ vs ΛC for oxalic acid.

pK₁ and pK₂ values in parenthesis.

^aFrom literature and ^bfrom extrapolation.

B = From Shedlovsky's equation.

C = From Kohlrausch's law.

The analysis of data using Fuoss (1978) equation³⁵ or Lee-Wheaton equation³⁶ was not attempted. Niazi *et al.*³⁷ reported the dissociation constants of benzoic acid and nitrobenzoic acids in ethanol + water mixtures (upto 70 mass% of ethanol). They used Lee-Wheaton conductance equation. Though K_a and Λ_0 of the acids in water agree well with the reported values (with almost no improvement) but the results are erratic in mixed solvents. Niazi *et al.* found extrapolations impossible at higher i.e. 60 and 70 mass% of ethanol.

It is to be noted that Fuoss³⁸ also criticized Fuoss (1978) equation and observed that the accurated theoretic

cal treatment in probably incapable of giving accurate experimental result. It has been observed that Fuoss (1978) equation or Lee-Wheaton equation is well-suited for the determination of the association constants of the electrolytes of the type R₄NX but not ideally suitable for the dissociations of weak electrolytes like $HX \rightleftharpoons H^+ + X^-$ and $HX^- \rightleftharpoons H^+ + X^{2-}$ particularly in mixed or non-aqueous solvents where the dissociation constants are low.

Barthel and co-workers^{39,40} performed the conductivity studies on aqueous solutions of tartaric acid, phosphoric acid and related electrolytes. They analysed the data using Quint-Viallard equation⁴¹ for unsymmetrical

electrolytes. According to them, "the data analysis, with the help of the Quint-Viallard conductivity equation for unsymmetrical electrolytes, requires a reliable set of temperature dependent limiting molar conductivities of all ions that are produced in the dissociation and hydrolysis reactions and the knowledge of all equilibrium constants for the ionic equilibria".

The limiting molar conductivity and other relevant data for oxalic acid are not available and no attempt has been made to analyze our data with the help of Quint-Viallard equation.

The second dissociation constant for the reaction (2)

were determined pH-metrically. The meter readings of neutralised solutions of KHOX were appropriately corrected to get H⁺ ion concentrations. The values were utilised to calculate K'₂. However, in order to get the thermodynamic dissociation constant K₂, the following modifications were made⁴². From eq. (4) we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_2 &= \log K'_2 + \log \gamma_{OX^{2-}} \\ &= \log K'_2 + AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu} + c\mu \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{or, } \log K'_2 - AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu} = \log K_2 - c\mu \quad (14)$$

The left hand side of the equation was plotted against μ to

Fig. 1. Plot of $(\log K'_2 - AZ^2 \sqrt{\mu})$ vs μ for determination of pK₂ values of oxalic acid in different wt% of 2-propanol in 2-propanol + water mixtures.

get log K_2 or K_2 (Fig. 1). A values in mixed solvents at

298 K were calculated from the relation $\frac{A'}{A} = \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon'}\right)^{3/2}$,

where $A = 0.509$ for water at 298 K.

The results are recorded in the Table 1.

The solubility product K_{sp} for an electrolyte like KHOX is

$$K_{sp} = a_{K^+} \cdot a_{HOX^-} = C_{K^+} \cdot C_{HOX^-} \cdot \gamma_{\pm}^2 \quad (15)$$

The values of γ_{\pm} were calculated using both

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = -AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu} \quad (\text{Debye-Hückel limiting law}) \quad (16)$$

and

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{-AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \bar{a}B \sqrt{\mu}} \quad (\text{Debye equation with } \bar{a}B = 1) \quad (17)$$

\bar{a} = ion size parameter of the order 10^{-8} cm, B is a constant dependent on solvent and temperature and is equal to 3.33×10^8 for water at 298 K. $\bar{a}B$ in taken to be 1 in our calculations.

Davies⁴³ equation $\log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{-AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + c\mu$ could not be used as the values of c are likely to differ with solvent composition.

The Gibbs energies of transfer (from water to 2-PrOH + H₂O mixtures) for neutral oxalic acid, KHOX and for the reactions (1) and (2) represented by the relations¹⁸⁻²¹, are given in tables.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}_2\text{OX}) &= -2.303 RT \log \frac{C_S}{C_W} \times \frac{\gamma_S(\text{H}_2\text{OX})}{\gamma_W(\text{H}_2\text{OX})} \\ &\simeq -2.303 RT \log \frac{C_S}{C_W} \\ &= -2.303 RT \log m \gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{OX}} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0(\text{KHOX}) &= -2.303 RT \log \frac{s K_{sp}}{w K_{sp}} \\ &= -2.303 RT \log m \gamma_{\text{KHOX}} \\ &= -2.303 RT \log m \gamma_{\pm}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0(1) &= \Delta G_s^0(1) - \Delta G_w^0(1) \\ &= 2.303 RT \log \frac{m \gamma_{\text{H}^+} \cdot m \gamma_{\text{HOX}^-}}{m \gamma_{(\text{H}_2\text{OX})}} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0(2) &= \Delta G_s^0(2) - \Delta G_w^0(2) \\ &= 2.303 RT \log \frac{m \gamma_{\text{H}^+} \cdot m \gamma_{\text{OX}^{2-}}}{m \gamma_{\text{HOX}^-}} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $m\gamma_i$ etc. represents the 'medium effect' of the respective ion. C_S and C_W are the molar concentrations of H₂OX in the saturated solutions of oxalic acid in solvent (S) and water (W) respectively. Appropriate corrections were made for the dissociation of a fairly strong acid like oxalic acid in aqueous and mixed solvents. The activity coefficients $\gamma_{S(\text{H}_2\text{OX})}$ and $\gamma_{W(\text{H}_2\text{OX})}$ of saturated oxalic acid solutions are taken to be unity (by convention) where the activity coefficients refer to the standard states in the respective solvents.

The expressions (18-21) are the measures of the differences between solute-solvent interactions (of the species involved) in the two ideal reference states with the ion-ion or solute-solute interactions eliminated⁴⁴. pK_1 and pK_2 values in 2-propanol obtained via extrapolation are 4.24 and 8.32 respectively at 298 K (Fig. 2).

Discussion

Comparison of the results on the solubility of oxalic acid, potassium oxalate, pK_1 and pK_2 values in 2-PrOH + H₂O mixture is not possible due to non-availability of the data.

The solubility values of oxalic acid (Table 3) show somewhat anomalous behaviour. Due to ionic nature of oxalic acid, the solubility though decreases slightly initially, increases with the increase in organic co-solvent but the solubility values in general are lower than those in MeOH + H₂O and EtOH + H₂O mixtures of similar compositions. The same is true for the solubility of potassium hydrogen oxalate. These are obviously due to low dielectric constant of 2-PrOH + H₂O mixtures. However, correlation of solubility with different types of interactions as suggested by Shinoda⁴⁵ could not be made. Λ_0 -values of all the electrolytes decrease appreciably as the concentration of organic co-solvent increases which lowers the mobility of H⁺ ion and other ions considerably.

Fig. 2. Plot of pK₁ and pK₂ values of oxalic acid against (a) 1/ε × 10² and (b) mole fraction of 2-propanol in 2-propanol + water mixtures.

Variation of the Walden product of electrolytes $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ (Table 6) with solvent composition may be utilised to derive useful information regarding solute-solvent interactions. $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ -values of the electrolytes usually pass through a maximum in the region 25.1–34.3 wt% of 2-PrOH ($X_2 = 0.09$ – 0.13) for HClO₄ and KClO₄, but in the region of 16–25 wt% of 2-PrOH ($X_2 = 0.05$ – 0.09) for KHOX and oxalic acid though the viscosity⁸ is maximum in the region of 54 wt% of 2-PrOH ($X_2 \approx 0.26$). The results can be attributed to structural variations of the 2-PrOH + H₂O mixtures. But the main factor is the enormous decrease in λ_0^+ and λ_0^- values of ions arising from the restriction of mobility of H⁺ ion and other ions with the addition of 2-PrOH to water.

As expected, both pK₁ and pK₂ increase steadily with increase in percentage of 2-propanol (Table 3). However, initial increase in pK₁ value is less at least upto 16–25 wt% compared to those in MeOH + H₂O and EtOH + H₂O mixtures. This is probably due to the ionic nature of the solute. However, the increase pK₂ values with solvent composition is more pronounced.

As in the case of other alcohols, pK-values were found to be almost linear when plotted against 1/ε and mole fraction of 2-PrOH (Fig. 2) though deviations occur at higher percentages.

The effect of solvent on the first and second dissociations of oxalic acid is reflected in the change in the dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 and can be correlated with the 'medium effect' (with ion-ion interactions eliminated⁴⁴) and solute-solvent interactions of the components but no useful correlation can be made with the solvent property.

The acidity constants or the dissociation constants of oxalic acid in water and 2-PrOH + H₂O mixtures are influenced by

- (i) The strengths of the $\begin{array}{c} \text{COOH} \\ | \\ \text{COOH} \end{array}$ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COOH} \end{array}$ bonds
- (ii) The electronegativities of $\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COOH} \end{array}$ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COO}^- \end{array}$
- (iii) The factors stabilizing $\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COOH} \end{array}$ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COO}^- \end{array}$ ions compared to their conjugate acids
- (iv) The nature of the solvents

Of these, the last two factors are responsible for the changes in the behaviour of the acids in aquo + binary

mixtures. The changes in the dissociation constants may be due to

(a) The increase in basicity of the 2-PrOH + H₂O mixtures.

(b) The decrease in relative permittivity of dielectric constants of the medium with increasing 2-PrOH percentages (Table 1).

(c) Change in anion $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COOH} \end{array} \right)$ and $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{COO}^- \\ | \\ \text{COO}^- \end{array} \right)$ stabilization

The factor (a) increases the dissociation process. Addition of 2-PrOH to water is found to increase the basicity of the mixed solvents which passes through a maximum in the region ~64–75 wt% of 2-PrOH beyond which the basicity gradually decreases⁴⁶. However, the effect is probably small.

The factor (b) favours association, the lower the dielectric constant the greater will be the association. The factor (b) have more pronounced effect than (a) leading to a continuous increase in pK₁ and pK₂ values. The differences of anion-stabilization resulting from the structural characteristics of the aquo-binary mixtures and the variation of solute-solvent interactions also cause the variation of the dissociation constants. Anions are usually stabilized by hydrogen bonding in aqueous solutions and anion solvation is expected to decrease with increasing 2-PrOH concentration leading to the increase in pK₁ and pK₂ values.

The transfer Gibbs energy changes for the reactions (1) and (2) give some idea regarding the solvent effect on the dissociation of the acid but in order to comprehend ion-solvent interactions better and quantitatively, single ion Gibbs energies transfer (or medium effects of the individual components) were derived as follows :

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}_2\text{OX}) \quad (22)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-) = \Delta G_t^0(1) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}_2\text{OX}) \quad (23)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta G_t^0(\text{OX}^{2-}) = \Delta G_t^0(2) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-) \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{K}^+) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{KHOX}) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-) \quad (25)$$

$\Delta G_t^0(1)$, $\Delta G_t^0(2)$, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}_2\text{OX})$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{KHOX})$ are

experimentally determined. $\Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-)$, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{OX}^{2-})$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{K}^+)$ are thus obtained utilizing $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$, values from the previous works in our laboratory⁴⁷.

Uncertainty in the single ion values arises mainly from the uncertainties in $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values determined using extrathermodynamic assumptions with inherent limitations. However, the single ion values can never be absolute. Even the reported values of ionic hydrations are widely divergent.

Assuming an uncertainty to the extent of ± 0.5 kJ mol⁻¹ for $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$, uncertainty may be of the order of ± 0.5 to 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹ for $\Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-)$, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{OX}^{2-})$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{K}^+)$.

Gibbs energy changes of transfer for single ions give the trend of their relative variations with the solvent composition, being collectively dependent on solvent basicity, dipole moment, polarizability, refractive index, dielectric constant and a host of other parameters of uncertain magnitude²³⁻²⁵. Single ion values also represent the quantitative measures of ion-solvent interactions. Collection of a large number of data on single ions may give insight regarding the factors associated with ion-solvent interactions and their proper correlation.

The results indicate that $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(2)$ are increasingly positive or unfavourable in going from water to 2-PrOH + H₂O mixtures inspite of the fact that $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}_2\text{OX})$ are increasingly negative or favourable. $\Delta G_t^0(\text{HOX}^-)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{OX}^{2-})$ are positive and monotonically increase with solvent composition (Table 4). This may be related to lower dielectric constants of the binary mixtures and probably lesser hydrogen-bonding capability of the binary mixtures compared to water resulting in lesser stabilizing effect on the anions. The effect is more pronounced with increase in charge.

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{K}^+)$ is favourable (-ve) initially but becomes increasingly unfavourable (+ve) with increasing 2-PrOH concentration though a decrease at 34 wt% ($x_2 = 0.13$) has been noted (Table 5). ΔG_t^0 values of the ions are, however, not available for comparison.

There are important limitations for determining ΔG_t^0 , (K^+) based on solubility values. $\Delta G_t^0(\text{KHOX})$ values calculated using Debye-Hückel limiting law and Debye-Hückel equation (with $aB = 1$) (Table 5) are obviously different and we prefer values based on Debye-Hückel equation. However, ionic strengths of the solutions in water and

Table 4. Free energy of transfer (kJ mol⁻¹) of anion ΔG⁰_t (OX²⁻) of oxalic acid in (2-propanol + H₂O) mixtures at 298 K

2-Propanol (wt%)	ΔG ⁰ _t (H ⁺)	ΔG ⁰ _t (H ₂ OX)		ΔG ⁰ _t (HOX ⁻)			ΔG ⁰ _t (OX ²⁻)		
		Calculated ^a	Corrected	ΔG ⁰ _t (1)	Calculated ^a	Corrected	ΔG ⁰ _t (2)	Calculated ^a	Corrected
8.0	-1.16	+0.17	+0.01	1.54	2.86	2.71	3.20	7.22	7.07
16.3	-2.03	+0.06	-0.16	2.05	4.14	3.92	4.74	10.91	10.69
25.1	-3.60	-0.01	-0.27	2.62	6.21	3.95	6.28	16.09	15.83
34.3	-4.31	-0.14	-0.47	3.54	7.71	7.38	7.76	19.78	19.45
43.9	-5.15	-0.26	-0.67	5.14	10.03	9.62	9.76	24.94	24.53
54.0	-5.50	-0.29	-0.74	6.56	11.77	11.32	11.81	29.08	28.63
64.6	-5.63	-0.31	-0.82	9.24	14.56	14.05	14.21	34.40	33.89
75.8	-5.08	-0.38	-0.91	10.44	15.14	14.61	17.06	37.28	36.75
87.5	-3.25	-0.47	-1.03	13.01	15.79	15.23	19.00	38.04	37.48

^aCalculated from experimental solubility data without correction for dissociation of oxalic acid.

Table 5. Free energy of transfer (kJ mol⁻¹) of cation ΔG⁰_t (K⁺) of KHOX in (2-propanol + H₂O) mixtures at 298 K

2-Pro- panol (wt%)	Solubility (C _i)		f _±		K _s		ΔG ⁰ _t = -RT ln K _s		ΔG ⁰ _{t(s←w)}		ΔG ⁰ _t (HOX ⁻)		ΔG ⁰ _t (K ⁺)	
	(mol dm ⁻³)	μ	(I)	(II)	(I)	(II)	(I)	(II)	(I)	(II)	(I)	(II)	(I)	(II)
0	0.415	0.415	0.470	0.632	0.038	0.069	8.10	6.63	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.0	0.260	0.260	0.515	0.644	0.018	0.028	9.97	8.86	1.87	2.23	2.71	-0.84	-0.48	
16.3	0.201	0.201	0.512	0.630	0.011	0.016	11.27	10.24	3.17	3.61	3.92	-0.75	-0.31	
25.1	0.144	0.144	0.521	0.623	5.62×10 ⁻³	8.05×10 ⁻³	12.84	11.95	4.74	5.32	3.95	0.79	1.37	
34.3	0.096	0.096	0.528	0.614	2.57×10 ⁻³	3.48×10 ⁻³	14.78	14.03	6.68	7.40	7.38	-0.7	0.02	
43.9	0.061	0.061	0.538	0.607	1.07×10 ⁻³	1.37×10 ⁻³	16.95	16.34	8.85	9.71	9.62	-0.77	0.09	
54.0	0.040	0.040	0.522	0.582	4.36×10 ⁻⁴	5.42×10 ⁻³	19.17	18.64	11.07	12.01	11.32	-0.25	0.69	
64.6	0.020	0.020	0.534	0.577	1.14×10 ⁻⁴	1.33×10 ⁻³	22.49	22.11	14.39	15.48	14.05	0.34	1.43	
75.8	0.009	0.009	0.556	0.585	2.51×10 ⁻⁵	2.77×10 ⁻⁵	26.25	26.00	18.15	19.37	14.61	3.54	4.76	
87.5	0.0036	0.0036	0.607	0.624	4.77×10 ⁻⁶	5.05×10 ⁻⁶	30.36	30.22	22.26	23.59	15.23	7.03	8.36	
100	0.0018	0.0018	0.637	0.649	1.31×10 ⁻⁶	1.36×10 ⁻⁶	33.56	33.47	25.46	26.84	-	-	-	

(I) $\log f_{\pm} = -AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu}$ ($Z_+ = Z_- = 1$)

$K_s = a_i^2$

μ = Ionic strength, γ_± = mean activity coefficient.

$a_i = c_i f_{\pm}$

(II) $\log f_{\pm} = \frac{-AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$

water-rich mixtures are high. Naturally an error in γ_± values may be likely. The changes in ΔG⁰_t (K⁺) values may be due to initial structure formation of water by 2-PrOH and subsequent structural breakdown of water molecules and preferential solvation of K⁺ by water molecules. The changes in basicities of the solvent mixtures and positive charging effect also contribute to ΔG⁰_t (K⁺).

It is apparent that the study of the ion-solvent interactions and the determination of single ion Gibbs energies of transfer are of great importance to understand the different aspects of solution chemistry. It is also desirable to

determine ΔG⁰_t (1) by different methods to arrive at a consistent set of single ion data.

It is seen that ΔG⁰_t (ion) values (determined here) can be utilised for predicting ΔG⁰_t (K₂OX) which is equal to [2ΔG⁰_t (K⁺) + ΔG⁰_t (OX²⁻)] in different percentages of binary mixtures. The data can also be utilised to calculate single ion (Gibbs) energies of transfer of other ions.

Moreover, ΔG⁰_t (ion) values can be dissected further as follows :

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{ion}) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{cav}) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{Born}) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{ion-})$

dipole) + ΔG_t^0 (ion-induced dipole) + ΔG_t^0 (ion-quadrupole) + other terms (26)

Other terms may represent structural and chemical interactions.

The theoretical calculations of the different terms can hardly be regarded to be absolute. In spite of limitations, valuable information associated with solution chemistry can be ascertained from the collection of single ion data.

Accurate pK_1 and pK_2 values can be utilised to prepare buffers in the low pH-region. Moreover, standard buffers of known pH values can be obtained from the relation,

$$pH = \frac{1}{2} pK_1 + \frac{1}{2} pK_2 + 2 \log f_{\pm} \quad (27)$$

using $NaHC_2O_4$ or KHC_2O_4 solutions of low ionic strengths.

It is expected that the studies on the solvent effect on the dissociation constants should give some valuable information regarding the structural properties of the mixed solvents.

However, ΔG_t^0 (i) of solutes from aqueous to aquo + organic mixtures are usually monotonic and due to compensation of ΔH_t^0 (i) and $T\Delta S_t^0$ (i)⁴⁰ terms having well defined extremum with mirror-image relationship to each other. Moreover, solvent reorganisation contributions to the entropy and energy of solvation that arises from solute induced perturbations in solvent structure averaged over a large number of solvent molecules giving rise to non-vanishing solvent-solvent interaction energy contributions, get cancelled in the free energy of solvation⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰.

In spite of no decisive models of water structure, it is known that liquid water is an equilibrium mixture of quasi-tetrahedral structures i.e. 'icebergs' of short life time and small volumes⁵¹ of dense non-hydrogen bonded water molecules and there is a sensitive order-disorder balance within liquid water which is disturbed by ions as well as co-solvent molecules.

Alcohol molecules, on the other hand, are bifunctional in nature containing hydroxyl group (which may cause solute-solvent hydrogen bonding) and hydrophobic alkyl group (which may cause hydrophobic hydration) in binary mixtures. Alcohols also form two bonds – each O-atom acting as donor and acceptor though unfavourable steric effect (which increases with the size of the alkyl

groups) restricts the degree of order and precludes three dimensional association⁵².

Specific hydration (by OH group) depending on the mutual orientation and relative distance between potential hydration sites

and non-specific hydrophobic interactions (by alkyl group) may play dominant roles in solvation processes. Both compete for water structure organisations. The hydrophobic effect increases with the increase in size of the hydrophobic group whereas specific hydration effect acts in the opposite direction being greatest for strongly hydrated ions⁵³⁻⁵⁶. Thus, the maximum structure formation gradually shifts towards the water-rich region as we move from methanol to isopropanol. For alcohol + water mixtures, ΔH^M (-ve) is maximum at $x_2 \approx 0.3$ for MeOH but at $x_2 \approx 0.1$ for 1-PrOH (presumably for 2-PrOH). But ΔG^E , the excess Gibbs energy of mixing (+ve) is nearly symmetrical about $x_2 = 0.5$ is a function of negative and unsymmetrical enthalpy and entropy of mixing. Naturally, $T\Delta S^E$ should be more negative (than ΔH^M) and negative maximum (indicating structure formation) should move more towards greater x_2 (compared to ΔH^M)⁵².

The results can be rationalized in terms of structure formation of H_2O with the addition of alcohol molecules. Structure formation of water becomes maximum after which structural breakdown of polymeric water molecules as well as alcohol molecules takes place leading to water-alcohol bond. Ultimately structure formation of alcohols with total collapse of water structure occurs⁵².

It has been found that for 2-PrOH + H_2O mixtures, maximum in ultrasonic absorption and viscosity occurs at $x \approx 0.257$ indicating the start of structural breakdown.

Structural aspects are not well-reflected in ΔG_t^0 (1), ΔG_t^0 (2), ΔG_t^0 (HOX⁻) and ΔG_t^0 (OX²⁻) but probably reflected in ΔG_t^0 (H⁺) and ΔG_t^0 (K⁺) but definitely reflected in $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ of the electrolytes (Table 6) though $\lambda^+\eta_0$ or $\lambda^-\eta_0$ should give better information of structural aspects. Thus, ΔG_t^0 (HOX⁻) and ΔG_t^0 (OX²⁻) are posi-

tive and are net structure breakers i.e. ions break more structure in the mixed solvent than in water but reverse is true for $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ ions.

Table 6. Walden products Λ_0^0 (in $S\text{ cm}^2\text{ equiv}^{-1}\text{ P}$) of electrolytes and oxalic acid in 2-propanol + H_2O mixtures at 298 K

2-Propanol (wt%)	$HClO_4$	$KClO_4$	KH oxalate	Oxalic acid
0	3.718	1.259	0.987	3.482
8.0	4.460	1.398	0.978	4.111
16.3	4.819	1.437	1.122	4.487
25.1	5.155	1.458	1.098	4.489
34.3	4.481	1.630	0.940	3.936
43.9	4.104	1.448	0.802	3.334
54.0	3.268	1.227	0.676	2.527
64.6	2.239	1.037	0.563	1.729
75.8	1.986	0.835	0.429	1.574
87.5	1.360	0.648	0.322	0.924

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